

Prevalence of Cognitive Impairment in Individuals with Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease

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Abstract:

Introduction: COPD and cognitive impairment are prevalent conditions that have been extensively researched on their own however, data on COPD-related cognitive impairments has been expanding recently. An analysis of patient records from a sizable primary care practice revealed that COPD patients had a greater frequency of cognitive impairment than patients without COPD. One of the pathophysiological changes linked to COPD exacerbations is elevated systemic and airway inflammation. Hospital admissions for COPD exacerbations typically result in limits in cognitive function. A tiny percentage of this impairment will improve, which is beneficial, but as time goes on, the patient's cognition and memory will decline. Severe cases of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) are associated with higher rates of death and morbidity.

Materials and Method: The present study aimed to assess cognitive impairment in COPD patients aged 30 to 60. They were classified as homemakers, semiskilled and skilled workers. Using our inclusion and exclusion criteria, 200 males and 50 females from the Department of Respiratory Medicine were selected. To ascertain cognitive impairment, a mini-mental state examination was performed.

Results: This affirms that there is severe cognitive dysfunction in a larger percentage of the group of COPD patients. Cigarette smoking should be avoided among the COPD patients. Statistically, the results strongly suggest that smoking is a significant factor contributing to lower FEV1/FVC ratio in all stages of COPD (Mild, Moderate, and Severe). This investigation also provides evidence of a relationship between pulmonary function and COPD with cognitive impairment. For the evidence of cognitive function in smokers and non-smokers a comparative study was conducted in between (Mild, Severe, No Evidence), the p-values are extremely small (less than 0.001). This indicates an insignificant difference in MMSE scores between smokers and non-smokers.

Conclusion: There is a high prevalence of cognitive impairment among COPD patients. Patient care givers should be aware of symptoms such as trouble in concentrating, remembering, and decision-making, which hinder our daily activity. Further research on cognitive impairment in AECOPD patients needs to be analysed.

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Introduction

According to the World Health Organization (WHO) reports which were updated on March 2023, Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) is the primary cause of death all over the globe. The notable deaths during 2019 were 3.23 million. COPD is often associated with coexisting diseases such as cardiovascular disease, osteoporosis, and anemia for many years. It has most recently been discovered that it is largely correlated with cognitive impairment like social and psychological problems [1].

The severity of (COPD) was not studied in detail as there were airflow limitations and the use of poor markers largely did not impact the multi-nature of

the disease. Hence there is a need to characterize the full clinical spectrum for a better understanding, identification, and assessment of all the suspected comorbidities in COPD [2]. Cognitive impairments are the most suspected comorbidity which according to recent research contributes to acquired disability [3,4], the need for a caregiver [5], and non-adherence to reduced clinical benefits leading to poor outcomes [6] explicit probabilities of death in the COPD population [7,8].

The term "cognition" is outlined as a group of mental processes that enable someone to comprehend and use new knowledge gained from experience and reasoning to modify behaviour in response to

certain circumstances in a particular setting [9]. Several distinct domains include language, learning and memory, motor function, executive function, attention, and emotion. Intellectual and personal skills are determined by certain functional capacities within each cognitive area. A deterioration or malfunction in one or more cognitive domains, such as executive functioning, memory, and attention, is referred to as cognitive impairment [10].

According to recent research, those who have lung impairment (such as chronic lung disorders) are more likely to experience cognitive decline [11]. This may happen as a direct result of the airflow restriction or indirectly because individuals with lung disorders share risk factors. Numerous studies have examined the correlation between lung function metrics and cognitive deterioration in older adults [12].

A COPD exacerbation is not an infection, but rather a natural event in the course of this disease; it is characterized by changes from baseline dyspnoea, cough, and /or sputum that are greater than normal day-to-day variations (i.e. acute onset). The symptoms include hypoxia, increased heart rate, wheezing, decreased breath, speaking in short sentences, tripod position, and altered mental status. Common triggers for COPD exacerbation were bacterial pneumonia, respiratory viruses, air pollution, and med non-adherence [13].

The present study aimed to assess cognitive impairment in 30-60-year-old COPD patients from the Department of Respiratory Medicine, they were chosen according to our inclusion and exclusion criteria. A mini-mental state exam was conducted to determine cognitive impairment. We noticed that cognitive dysfunction is not uncommon in COPD patients, which will influence health status and prognosis with no corresponding treatment. Although poor general health (e.g., cigarette smoking) was a major associated risk factor for cognitive dysfunction because it is intricately related to the primary indicator of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD). Results were tabulated and subjected to statistical analysis.

Materials and Methods

A cross-sectional study was conducted among the COPD outpatients attending the respiratory medicine outpatient department at the Faculty of Medicine, Sri Lalithambigai Medical College and Hospital, approved by the Institute Ethical Committee (IEC - EC/NEW/INST/2022/2769). Patients who met the study's inclusion and exclusion criteria over a period of one year were considered for the study. The sample size along with a precision/ absolute error of 10% and the prevalence of factors causing visual memory dysfunction were calculated. The inclusion criteria were (a) patients willing to give consent (b) patients diagnosed with COPD using

the global initiative for chronic obstructive lung disease (GOLD) guidelines (c) patients who are between the age of 30 -60 years, any gender. The exclusion criteria were (a) patients who were not willing to give consent (b) patients who were diagnosed with mental illness or cognitive dysfunction(c) patients having other pulmonary diseases. met the study's inclusion and exclusion criteria were

Ethical approval was obtained from the institutional ethical committee. The patients were selected according to our inclusion criteria. A socio-demographic proforma and written informed consent form (CF) were collected from 250 patients for the test samples required to conduct tests. Demographic data for our study included age, gender, occupation, and smoking status. COPD status included mild, moderate, severe, and very severe (using pulmonary function test) other tests conducted on each patient were chest x-ray, CT scan, and sputum culture for further confirmation. Patients who had severe COPD symptoms were further diagnosed for COPD exacerbation, tests such as sputum analysis, ABG (oxygen vital signs), and level of dyspnoea, and the MMSE score was re-analysed. We found instances of COPD, in the study participants who showed COPD symptoms and had results indicating chronic airflow blockage (post-bronchodilator FEV1/FVC<0.70) following the guidelines set by the Global Initiative, for Chronic Obstructive Lung Disease (GOLD). Tests were conducted thrice with the highest readings noted and presented as a percentage of the expected value.

Cognitive function test: Cognitive abilities were evaluated through the mental state exam (MMSE) which is a well-established and commonly used tool, for gauging overall cognitive performance. The higher MMSE scores that are from (24-30) indicate the cognitive functioning of the patient is better, and MMSE scores from (18-23) are considered to have a mild cognitive functioning impairment. A score of (0-17) indicates a severe cognitive dysfunction.

Statistical Analysis: The gathered information was reviewed and organized in Microsoft Excel as data. Then analysed using the Statistical Package, for Social Science (SPSS 25.1, for Windows; SPSS Inc., Chicago, IL). The analysis was compared based on the data collected for each parameter.

Results

A total of 250 patients participated in this study, the demographic data were collected from Subjects of 30-60 years of age. Their occupation was categorized as semiskilled, skilled, and homemakers. 200 male and 50 female COPD patients from the Department of Respiratory Medicine, were chosen according to our inclusion

and exclusion criteria. The participants did not have any co-morbidities. When the smoking status was calculated we found that 60% of COPD male patients were smoking 8% of COPD female patients were smoking and the rest of the participants were non-smokers. The COPD status included mild, moderate, and severe, (using pulmonary function test) and other tests conducted

on each patient were chest x-ray, CT scan, and sputum culture for further confirmation.

The comparative analysis of the severity of smoking in COPD patients was studied with the non-smokers and they were tabulated and analyzed statistically (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Comparative study of COPD patients (smokers and non-smokers) with stages of COPD severity

The p-values are less than 0.05 in all three stages (mild, moderate, and severe) of COPD, suggesting a statistically significant difference in the FEV1/FVC ratio between smokers and non-smokers. This shows that smoking is a crucial factor. The decreased FEV1/FVC ratio shows smokers have a statistically significant reduction in lung function when compared to non-smokers. The study's subjects' severity did not significantly differ based on their age, gender, or occupation.

Cognitive function test

The researchers utilized the Mini Mental State Examination (MMSE) to assess abilities, in each group. This evaluation involved inquiries about awareness of time and location memorization of

three words, focus and arithmetic skills, recollection of the three words, after a pause, language comprehension, sentence reproduction, and visual perception tasks to gauge cognitive function. There are 20 activities in the MMSE test, and a higher total score suggests better cognitive performance (the maximum possible score is 30). A score of 26 to 30 represents 'normal cognitive functioning', and a score between 24 and 25 'borderline normal cognitive functioning'; less than a score of 24 indicates cognitively impaired, while severe impairment is indicated by scores less than or equal to 18. The scores were tabulated in (Table 1 and Figure 2).

Table 1: Comparison of MMSE scores between the smokers and non-smokers group

MMSE scores	Smokers	Non-smokers	F-statistic	p-value
Mild	60	17	1321.88	
Severe	74	8	6405.88	<000.1
No evidence	24	67	1081.6	

Figure 2: Comparison of MMSE scores between the smokers and non-smokers group

The p-values for the comparative study between (Mild, Severe, No Evidence) are incredibly modest (less than 0.001), examining the evidence of cognitive function in smokers and non-smokers. This suggests that the MMSE score differences between smokers and non-smokers were quite small. All of the examples have rather big F-statistics. This lends more credence to the idea that the groups differ significantly from one another.

This comparison study concludes that COPD patients who smoked irrespective of age, gender, or the work they do, evidently contribute to the severity of cognitive dysfunction. The patients who were COPD patients and never smoked also had mild to severe cognitive MMSE scores. In conclusion, cognitive impairment is high in the smoking group. A larger group of study can conclude more evidently the difference between both the groups (Table 2 and Figure 3).

Table 2: Comparison of MMSE scores of cognitive impairment within groups

Groups	Within SS	Within DF	Mean Squares	p-value
Mild vs. Severe	3108.75	2	1554.375	0.955
Mild vs. No Evidence	1898	2	949	0.839
Severe vs. No Evidence	3122.75	2	1561.375	0.919

Figure 3: Comparison of MMSE scores of cognitive impairment within groups

When calculated the MMSE scores within groups (mild, severe, and no evidence). The p-values for all the group's tests are greater than 0.05 which suggests that we fail to reject the original hypothesis of a lack of significant difference in MMSE scores between groups. In other words, there is insufficient evidence to claim a significant effect of smoking status (mild cognitive, severe cognitive, or no evidence) on MMSE scores in this sample. These results also affirm that there is severe cognitive dysfunction in a larger percentage of the group of COPD patients.

COPD exacerbation analysis in severe COPD patients

The analysis was done on severe COPD patients. The change in the colour of the sputum is the first sign of COPD exacerbation as the colour changes from white to green, brown, or blood streaks. We found that most of the patients were coughing up brown-coloured sputum. The arterial blood gas analysis on the severe COPD showed that few patients in the group had high partial carbon-dioxide pressure and they were kept under ventilation until they were stable. The level of dyspnoea was analysed and was noted that all of them had severity on shortness of breath. These patients were further cross-checked for severity of cognitive impairment during their discharge and all the AECOPD patients had severe cognitive dysfunction and were advised for personal care and frequent hospital visits. Detailed analysis will be done to study the association of AECOPD patients with cognitive impairment with other tools in the future.

Discussion

A group of 250 patients participated in this study between 30-60 years of age were collected. Their occupation was categorized as semiskilled, homemakers, skilled and unemployed. Patients were chosen according to our inclusion and exclusion criteria. The participants did not have any comorbidities. There was a comparison of the COPD patients who smoked and non-smokers who contributed the cognitive impairment. This study also concludes that there is very large evidence of the proportion of cognitive dysfunction in COPD patients. We have also found that smoking COPD patients contributed higher MMSE scores than the ones who did not smoke. Adjusting for confounders, there was a 1.9-fold greater coded prevalence of cognitive impairment in COPD patients versus subjects without COPD [14].

Recent estimates suggest that 4% of older patients, aged 65 and above, with mild COPD, have cognitive impairment, and up to 61% of those with severe hypoxemia; only the latter correlate show significance between groups [15]. This large difference could be explained by the fact that COPD severity might have been a contributing factor [16], whether cognitive impacts were not assessed systematically but self-reported, and different diagnostic criteria and tools used to determine CI in later time points [17]. Different threshold definitions for cognitive impairment even when using the same cognitive assessment tool, studies used different thresholds or no specific reference values to define cognitive outcomes. Perhaps the most noteworthy finding in our study is that age, occupation or gen-

der did not have any correlation with the severity of the cognitive impairment.

The implication of a previous study, it was noted that patients with COPD based on their age had a significant rise in cognitive impairment or dementia in young people (aged < 65 years). Nevertheless, it noted that their results were given a small number of studies available for subgroup analysis, and substantial heterogeneity in a larger group of patients is a criterion for a better understanding of the correlation between COPD and cognitive disorder [18].

Previous studies showed that both poor lung function and decreased cognition are interrelated through shared risk factors (e.g. smoking) and may account for the observed associations between them [19]. Short-term impacts on cognitive function are convoluted with acute nicotine intake, enhancing the cognition of smokers, while its absence may lead to impairments in cognition [20]. By systematic progression, subsequent long-term studies reveal another remarkable finding: low childhood IQs are associated with increased smoking risks, and subsequently, poor cognitive scores are found in ageing smokers, compared to ex-smokers who had never smoked [21]. Consequently, strategies that help people stop smoking should be targeted not only in public health interventions for lung function but also towards preserving or increasing cognitive capacity [22]. This study complements our study on smoking status as it has a great impact on COPD patients and a higher risk of cognitive impairment than people who do not smoke. Rates of mild cognitive impairment range up to 36% in patients with moderate-to-severe COPD, primarily affecting executive function, memory, and attention. Lastly, Dodd et.al has also shown in a cohort study that executive dysfunction is related to heavy smoking and severe tobacco consumption by patients suffering from COPD [23].

COPD is a multisystem disease with numerous extrapulmonary complications. The implication of a high risk for cognitive impairment is particularly profound among hypoxemic patients. A cognitive assessment should be performed in patients with COPD by clinicians, so they can identify which patients could benefit most from interventions. Similarly, our study showed the high risk of cognitive impairment in severe COPD patients having hypoxemia and dyspnoea [24].

Strengths and limitations

The strength of our study is that we found that positive association between COPD patients and cognitive impairments. These patients were chosen without co-morbidities. We also found that the smoking history of the COPD patients increased the severity of cognitive dysfunction. Limitations were to understand the association of COPD patients and cognitive impairment with gender as a criterion

there should be equal participation of female patients in future studies. More methodologies should be implemented and studied.

Conclusion

Results show that there is a high prevalence of cognitive impairment among COPD patients. This raises awareness to be addressed as cognitive impairment can cause trouble in concentrating, remembering, and decision making and it becomes a hindrance in doing our daily activity. Future studies should evaluate whether the provision of cognitive interventions may increase participation in daily activities among the patients. Cigarette smoking should be avoided among the COPD patients. This investigation provides evidence of a relationship between pulmonary function and COPD with cognitive impairment. Future research should address the management of cognitive impairment among these COPD patients. Tests should be conducted to analyse cognitive impairment in AECOPD patients.

References

1. Calverley PM: Neuropsychological deficits in chronic obstructive pulmonary disease. *Monaldi Arch Chest Dis.* 1996, 51:5-6.
2. Jones PW, Agusti AG: Outcomes and markers in the assessment of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease. *Eur Respir J.* 2006, 27:822-32. [10.1183/09031936.06.00145104](https://doi.org/10.1183/09031936.06.00145104)
3. Hartley P, Gibbins N, Saunders A, et al.: The association between cognitive impairment and functional outcome in hospitalised older patients: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Age Ageing.* 2017, 46:559-567. [10.1093/ageing/afx007](https://doi.org/10.1093/ageing/afx007)
4. Martinez CH, Richardson CR, Han MK, et al.: Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, cognitive impairment, and development of disability: the health and retirement study. *Ann Am Thorac Soc.* 2014, 11:1362-70. [10.1513/AnnalsATS.201405-187OC](https://doi.org/10.1513/AnnalsATS.201405-187OC)
5. Fogg C, Meredith P, Bridges J, et al.: The relationship between cognitive impairment, mortality and discharge characteristics in a large cohort of older adults with unscheduled admissions to an acute hospital: a retrospective observational study. *Age Ageing.* 2017, 46:794-801. [10.1093/ageing/afx022](https://doi.org/10.1093/ageing/afx022)
6. Allen SC, Jain M, Ragab S, et al.: Acquisition and short-term retention of inhaler techniques require intact executive function in elderly subjects. *Age Ageing.* 2003, 32:299-302. [10.1093/ageing/32.3.299](https://doi.org/10.1093/ageing/32.3.299)
7. Campbell SE, Seymour DG, Primrose WR, et al.: A systematic literature review of factors affecting outcome in older medical patients admitted to hospital. *Age Ageing.* 2004, 33:110-5. [10.1093/ageing/afh036](https://doi.org/10.1093/ageing/afh036)

8. Marin MF, Lord C, Andrews J, et al.: Chronic stress, cognitive functioning and mental health. *Neurobiol Learn Mem.* 2011, 96:583-95.10.1016/j.nlm.2011.02.016
9. DeVito AJ: Dyspnea during hospitalizations for acute phase of illness as recalled by patients with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease. *Heart Lung.* 1990, 19:186-91.
10. Gurney-Smith B, Cooper MJ, Wallace LM: Anxiety and panic in chronic obstructive pulmonary disease: the role of catastrophic thoughts. *Cogn Ther Res.* 2002,26:143-55.10.1023/A: 1013854023665
11. Gueli N, Verrusio W, Linguanti A, et al.: Montelukast therapy and psychological distress in chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD): a preliminary report. *Arch Gerontol Geriatr.* 2011,52:36-9.10.1016/j.archger.2010.04.014
12. Fullerton DG, Suseno A, Semple S, et al.: Wood smoke exposure, poverty and impaired lung function in Malawian adults
13. Bajaj MK, Burrage DR, Tappouni A, Dodd JW, Jones PW, Baker EH. COPD patients hospitalized with exacerbations have greater cognitive impairment than patients hospitalized with decompensated heart failure. *Clin Interv Aging.* 2018 Dec18;14:1-8. doi: 10.2147/CIA.S185981. PMID: 30587948; PMCID: PMC63 02823.
14. R.A. Siraj a,b , T.M. McKeever a,b , J.E. Gibson b, A.L. Gordon c,d , C.E. Bolton a, Risk of incident dementia and cognitive impairment in patients with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD): A large UK population-based study
15. S.S. Chang, S. Chen, G.J. McAvay, M.E. Tinetti, Effect of coexisting chronic obstructive pulmonary disease and cognitive impairment on health outcomes in older adults, *J. Am. Geriatr. Soc.* 60 (10) (2012) 1839–1846.
16. A.M. Yohannes, W. Chen, A.M. Moga, I. Leroi, M.J. Connolly, Cognitive impairment in chronic obstructive pulmonary disease and chronic heart failure: a systematic review and meta-analysis of observational studies, *J. Am. Med. Dir. Assoc.* 18 (5) (2017) 451, e1-e11.
17. L. Schou, B. Ostergaard, L.S. Rasmussen, S. Rydahl-Hansen, K. Phanareth, Cognitive dysfunction in patients with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease—a systematic review, *Respir. Med.* 106 (8) (2012) 1071–1081.
18. Wang J, Li X, Lei S, Zhang D, Zhang S, Zhang H, Li J. Risk of dementia or cognitive impairment in COPD patients: A meta-analysis of cohort studies. *Front Aging Neurosci.* 2022 Sep 9;14:962562. doi: 10.3389/fnagi.2022.962562. PMID: 36158542; PMCID: PMC9500359.
19. Wołoszynowska-Fraser MU, Kouchmeshky A, McCaffery P. Vitamin A and retinoic acid in cognition and cognitive disease. *Annu Rev Nutr.* 2020;40:247–72. (19)Campos MW, Serebrisky D, Castaldelli-Maia JM. Smoking and cognition. *Curr Drug Abuse Rev.* 2016;9(2): 76–9.
20. Corley J, Gow AJ, Starr JM, Deary IJ. Smoking, childhood IQ, and cognitive function in old age. *J Psychosom Res.* 2012;73(2):132–8.
21. Higbee, D.H., Granell, R., Hemani, G. et al. Lung function, COPD and cognitive function: a multivariable and two sample Mendelian randomization study. *BMC Pulm Med* 21, 246 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12890-021-01611-6>
22. Campman CA, Sitskoorn MM. Better care for patients with COPD and cognitive impairment. *Lancet Respir Med.* 2013;1(7):504–506. doi:10.1016/S2213-2600(13)70163-2 PubMed Web of Science @Google Scholar
23. Dodd JW, Novotny P, Sciurba FC, Benzo RP. Executive function, survival, and hospitalization in chronic obstructive pulmonary disease. a longitudinal analysis of the National Emphysema Treatment Trial (NETT). *Ann Am Thorac Soc.* 2015;12(10):1473–1481. doi:10.1513/AnnalsATS.201506-373OC
24. Thakur N, Blanc PD, Julian LJ, Yelin EH, Katz PP, Sidney S, Iribarren C, Eisner MD. COPD and cognitive impairment: the role of hypoxemia and oxygen therapy. *Int J Chron Obstruct Pulmon Dis.* 2010 Sep 7;5:263-9. doi: 10.2147/copd.s10684. PMID: 20856825; PMCID: PMC2939681.